

THE EFFECT OF PARTITION ON INDIAN RAILWAY IN THE NOVELS TITLED TRAIN TO PAKISTAN AND TRAIN TO INDIA

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Abstract

In 2023 it becomes the headlines in almost all the leading newspapers in India that stones are being pelted on Vande-Bharat Express by some extremists and a few years before that protestors even set the train coaches on fire and thus the railway platforms were massacred in Bengal in 2019 to the extent that regular rail operations were suspended until the system was returned to a state of normalcy and the agitation caused over the issue of CAA and NRC was brought under control. Over a period of time the issues like minority rights, communalism have proved to be a bone of contention for the nation and the choice to protest against the government by the rebel troops on the sensitive issues has often taken the form of violence and intimidation. The disruption of rail operations needs to be viewed and analysed from this political perspective and this practise is not uncommon in the history of freedom struggle of India where the role of trains, since the days of partition and even before it, has become controversial on a point that railway serves to play the agent of British Raj at one hand, on the other it plays the role of a saviour of humanity during the days of partition. It plays the role of a government agent of migration to execute the order of partition and to do that it invokes the wrath of agitators to the level that it becomes the symbol of violence and even the companion of death that this paper is going to explore. Drawing upon the accounts from Train to Pakistan, an English fiction by Khushwant Singh and Train to India, a memoir by Maloy Krishna Dhar, this paper examines how trains became emblematic of the horrors of partition, as well as the challenges and opportunities they presented in the post-partition period.

Keywords: Partition, Trauma, Minority, Communalism, Identity

Introduction

With ‘a single stroke’ British India was divided into two separate nations in 1947 and this partition has not only divided geographical boundaries and cultural unity but also created refugee problem where millions of people are forced to migrate across the border as a result of which the world happens to see a biggest mass migration in history with two millions of

people dead and thousands of women raped and kidnapped. The joy of freedom was overshadowed instantly by the tumultuous noise of mass migration from Pakistan to India and vice-versa in the entire south Asia and it was in this uncertain situation that the Indian railway network played a pivotal role. But the division of nations did not spare the railway stations, tracks, engines, workshops, trains, related properties and the work forces from being divided into two separate parts belonging to two distinct countries. Railway work forces which was considered as one of the largest workforces in colonial India, numbering over one million experienced a sudden division that resulted in the scarcity of railway workers for which millions of people suffered during the journey because most of the people were not left with a wide choice of preference at the time other than railways which was considered as the most rapid and common mode of mass transportation. It was estimated that more than seven lakhs of helpless refugees travelled by train just after partition (within 23 days from August to September of 1947). Thus the impact of partition was not only limited to the problems of passengers due to the haphazard division of railways giving rise to a huge logistical complexity but the political division in the name of religion, instigating a horrific communal holocaust exacerbated the entire experience of train journey as the railway tracks, stations and buildings became the main target of those insurgent people. The railway network became the site of communal riots and violent killings. It was in this occasion that the historical trajectory of Indian railways, tracing its evolutions and changing perceptions from the British colonial period to the post-partition era must be examined. Though initially started off to oil the wheels of British economy the Indian railways with time turned out to be the platform of protest for the freedom fighters against the British Raj. In 1907 two consecutive attempts, though unsuccessful, were made to derail and bomb the train respectively carrying the notorious mastermind behind the partition of Bengal, Andrew Fraser who was the Lieutenant-Governor of Bengal from 1903 to 1908. Later in 1925, a train robbery at Kakori was executed by the revolutionaries of Hindustan Republican Association in order to strengthen the fund required for the activities of independence movement and the money looted was reported to be transporting from India to British treasury. In 1929 when Lord Irwin was travelling by a special train, revolutionaries tried to kill him by throwing bombs on it. Even before that connectivity system was disrupted by the attacks made on railway for a number of times near Chittagong in 1930. All this evident seek to justify that trains were viewed till the first half of the twentieth century as the symbols of colonial power in India. But the perspective changes when the father of nation, Gandhiji chose to travel by train for creating a unified nation

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around 1932. It is from then on that railways underwent a change and were instead perceived as the symbol of connectivity and development.

Critical Overview

Train to Pakistan delivers a gruelling pen picture of partition of India in 1947, a historic moment in entire history of humanity characterised by massive deportations, expulsions and inhuman violence. Khushwant Singh weaves together the personal narratives of individuals caught in the tumult of partition, foregrounding unforgettable marks on the lives of common human beings. Central to the narrative is the symbolism of the train and it becomes a significant metaphor for the partition experience. Mano Majra is a fictional village in Khushwant Singh's novel *Train to Pakistan*. It is situated on the border of India and Pakistan and here the lives of the common people are regulated by the arrival and departure of trains. This rural area, as the author asserts has become very special due to the presence of railways, "Mano Majra has always been known for its railway station" The train schedule has introduced a sense of discipline, a sense of order and punctuality in their traditional way of life. Their daily routines were modified and structured in a systematic way around the comings and goings of the trains as Singh says,

"Before daybreak, the mail train rushes through on its way to Lahore, and as it approaches the bridge, the driver invariably blows two long blasts on the whistle. In an instant, all Mano Majra comes awake....By the time 10:30 morning passenger train from Delhi comes in, life in ManoMajra has settled down to its full daily routine....As the midday express goes by, Mano Majra stops to rest....When evening passenger from Lahore comes in, everyone gets to work again....When the goods train streams in, they say to each other, 'There is the goods train.' It is like saying goodnight....The goods train takes a long time at the station, with the engine running up and down the sidings exchanging wagons. By the time it leaves, the children are asleep. The older wait for its rumble over the bridge to lull them to slumber. Then life in Mano Majra is stilled, save for the dogs barking at the trains that pass in the night."(Singh 4-6) K.R. Srinivasa Iyengar remarks,

"...indeed there are tens of thousands of villages like Mano Majra where the law has always been peaceful coexistence, and not communal strife. But 1947 was not like other times. Suspicion and violence filled the air, and an ill wind carried them even to little oases of communal harmony like Mano Majra."(Iyengar 498-499)

Regularity of the trains and their arrival on time was suddenly jeopardised in post-partition era where the delay and procrastination suggest the arrival of disturbances in the peaceful life of Mano Majra.

“Early in September the time schedule in Mano Majra started going wrong. Trains became less punctual than ever before and many more started to run through at night...People stayed in bed late without realizing that times had changed and mail train might not run through at all...In the evenings, everyone was indoors before sunset and in bed before the express came by—if it did come by. Goods trains had stopped running altogether, so there was no lullaby to lull them to sleep. Instead, ghost trains went past at odd hours between midnight and dawn, disturbing the dreams of Mano Majra.”(Singh81) But one day the arrival of a ghost train initiates a sudden change in their otherwise still and peaceful course of life.

“One morning, a train from Pakistan halted at Mano Majra railway station. At first glance, it had the look of the trains in the days of peace. No one sat on the roof. No one clung between the bogies. No one was balanced on the footboards. But somehow it was different. There was something uneasy about it. It had a ghostly quality.” (Singh82)

The train stops at Mano Majra railway station and it is found to be carried fifteen hundred dead bodies within. HukumChand , the magistrate comes to examine the train and comes across horrific visions. He narrates what he has seen. Human beings have clutched their own entrails. Dead women and children are staring each other wide-eyed. The compartments are full of the dead bodies of young passengers. It was unbearable for Hukum Chand to witness. During the time of partition, railways took the role of a funeral car that standing silently witnesses the scene of death and again moves. The arrival and departure of trains loses its rhythm as trains were running out of schedule. The trains were no longer the familiar agents of their happiness. They appear unexpectedly like the death comes and goes without knocking. For the villagers of Mano Majra the horn of trains no more functions like a clarinet call for their awakening from sleep or call for work. It is more like a horn of a hearse that they were not ready to hear at all. The sight of corpses arrived with the train aroused the state of bereavement among the beholders and before the situation is restored another train arrived from Pakistan causing further feeling of trauma and unrest among the villagers of Mano Majra. When they encountered a second train and they apprehended the possibility of dead bodies in the train like the former ghost train, their hearts started to palpitate. The atmosphere was changing over and it looked almost like a deserted land where there is no life. People have forgotten to breathe and survive here. The villagers were in constant fear of the further

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sight of death, a ghost train. Mano Majra became a place of death that the residents have never thought of or seen before. The violence, mistrust and death raises the question of brotherhood and the value of humanity. The atmosphere of the village suddenly changes as the people standing over there were contemplating on the future and they assumed that the counter attack is the only way left for them to exist. They were transformed from human beings to the predators who were left for do or die situation. They were determined to kill Muslims who will be travelling from India to Pakistan. A Sikh who was burning with the fire of vengeance turned up before the villagers and with a view to instigate the villagers of his community declared,

“Tomorrow a train load of Muslims is to cross the bridge to Pakistan. If you are men, this train should carry as many people dead to the other side as you have received.”(Singh159)

The sight of dead bodies littered with bruises and wounds invoked a sense of fear among the villagers and on understanding the rival force working behind such a heinous act a feeling of animosity caught hold of their imagination. A feeling of hatred and anger spiked in their mind for the opposite community with whom they so long have been staying in peace in the village. Familiar faces blurred in their vision as the feelings of love and empathy vanished. They were anticipating further mishap that might soon take place unknowingly on their own. With the advent of another train their anticipation might transform into a bitter reality. Here train functions as the destiny that will confirm their existence either in peace or in tragedy. That the train is playing the role of destiny is evident not only in the case of the beholders of the ghostly train but also for the passengers like Nooran who was travelling to an unfamiliar place where the future is waiting for her with possibilities and impossibilities both. Very interestingly the same train journey proves to be out of danger for Nooran only when Juggat sacrifices his life or at the cost of the life of her lover. The same train takes the toll of life of a person to ensure the prospect of life for the other. The sacrifice of life in the critical juncture of time unfolds another dimension of humanity that remains a good example of brotherhood for those who were suffering from the fever of communal disharmony. The sacrifice of Juggat Singh, a Sikh for the Muslim passengers unfurls a significant thematic preoccupation of the author that it is humanity and sacrifices that work as dominating forces in such a historic crucial circumstances.

“The engine was almost on him. There was a volley of shots. The man shivered and collapsed. The rope snapped in the centre as he fell. The train went over him, and went to Pakistan.(Singh 190)

The sight of train in "Train to Pakistan" comes out as a powerful sign of violence and disruption. It reflects the communal anxiety during the time of partition. Death is personified in the form of train as it appears with corpses unexpectedly and on the other side, some individuals fully utilize the availability of a system in their own way and they themselves involve in the heinous acts of murder and all other crimes against humanity. If we erase the arrival and departure episode of train from the plot it loses its symbolic meaning instantly. Thus the train, in the context of partition, plays a pivotal role. For the perpetrators it becomes a symbol of protest and for others, a site of terror and bloodshed, emblematic of the brutal consequences of communal hatred. Though the train is associated with violence and death, in "Train to Pakistan" it acts as a journey from hopelessness to hope and from chaos to peace. It is emancipation from bondage and a means of escape and oxygen for some characters who were desperately seeking for a shelter and were trying to break their troubled past. We can interpret the character of Nooran in this light. She is a Muslim character who falls in love with a Sikh whom she cannot marry. She is forced to marry a man of her community which she cannot accept. When a character like Nooran boards a train it becomes clear that she is searching a freedom, a better future where she can live life in her own terms. The train thus represents a freedom from the clutches of masculinity, emancipation from social bondage in the form of marriage. The train is served as the symbol of new life and a new beginning where there is no border, no chaos of partition and no violence.

With the exception of this catastrophic and cataclysmic aspect, the train in *Train to Pakistan* stands for the symbol of harmony. The account of entire train journey goes beyond communal borders and celebrates the values of human solidarity. In spite of the fact of overpowering animosity between Hindus, Muslims, and Sikhs, the train is viewed as a space where individuals have collected from diverse communities in moments of shared humanity. This is represented beautifully in the character of a Sikh gangster. Juggat Singh is such a human being who does not think twice to sacrifice his own life to save a trainload of Muslim refugees. Through this act of selfless deeds, the character of Juggat is critically discussed in a new light. Juggat does not bow down to the stereotypical rhetoric of communalism and reiterates the language of love and compassion across religious lines.

A similar narrative of partition is introduced in the story of *Train to India* by Maloy Krishna Dhar. Here train is none other than an emotional journey from known to the unknown. Search for order and peace in the tumultuous land of partition is cast over through the entire story of *Train to India* where the journey of a young boy who is no other than the author is

seen to travel with his mother from Bhairab to Dacca on the Dacca-Sylhet Express. The boy is frightened at the sight of blood and blood bob and his experience of train journey during the riot turned the compartment into a hell. In a chapter named *Train to Disaster*, the narrator while calling up the train journey with his uncle Birendra and his mother from Bhairab station utters,

“The train arrived on time. As we boarded the first class compartment I noticed a huge tick mark in white chalk on the side panel. This sight worried me. As one who often visited the station, I was acquainted with the passenger bogies. Only cargo bogies were often tick-marked below the name of the destination station. Ours was not a goods train. I dared not share the thought with my uncle.... Suddenly a liquid blob hit my face. Spit, I thought, normally relieved by passengers from the compartments ahead. I felt irritated and tried to remove the dirt with my left palm. It was fresh red blood. I wiped the blood with my palms and looked out to check the source.. A fat Marwari looking man with only an undergarment on his huge hulk was shouting at the top of his voice by raising one hand. His other hand was trying to stop the gushing blood from his punctured stomach. Obviously, he had been stabbed and pushed out of the compartment ahead of ours. Four more bodies with stab wounds, fountains of gushing blood and pitiable cries followed the first body... The Biharis, Kuttis and Ansars had attacked our train.” (Dhar 230-231) In the journey when the train is slowed down after passing the Anderson Bridge three men who looked like Bihari approached his uncle with the intention to loot and kill his uncle. The narrator along with his mother decides to jump off the train. “I looked out. We could not jump on the bridge girders. I looked out and saw several human bodies rolling down to the river below, all drenched with blood and severe wounds. I counted twenty bodies. The fearsome sight parched my throat. I tried to swallow my saliva. My fearful eyes caught the slow motion of a young woman clutching her baby and falling head down to the river below....” (Dhar 232-233) While the author was recollecting the past days he was shuddered with horror at the thought of terrible moments he chanced to encounter while he was travelling by train and he becomes unsuccessful to overcome a traumatic situation like this as he says,

“This time I failed to emerge out of the tunnel of my mind which appeared to be a pitch dark labyrinth. Frequent images of human bodies dropping out of the train flashed past my eyes. The frame of a mother, a child clinging to her bosom, repeatedly danced before my eyes. The ashen face and eyes of the young girl standing before the train window and crying for her father haunted me. How could a father leave his young daughter?” (Dhar 243) The narration

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was so enthralling that it compels the readers to delve deep into the larger historical and socio-political context of partition where political unrest and communal violence took a heavy toll on life.

In the context of partition, a time of violence and displacement the train journey, serving both as the facilitator of mass migration and as the sites of violence unmistakably occupy a central place in the collective memory of survivors and their subsequent generations and thus underscores the complexities of politics, identity and belonging in the history of a nation like India. The infamous train massacres like that of the 'Punjab Mail' or the 'Rawalpindi Express' serve as the stark reminders of how communal tensions, surprisingly enough, erupt from the religious identity of an individual. Thus the role of trains have undergone a constant shift, first from transportation and connectivity to progress and unity and then to fear and loss. Notwithstanding the challenges the partition presents opportunities to rethink and revitalize the railway infrastructure by promoting the integration and economic growth of newly independent nations.

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